

Dartmouth SYNERGY

Description

Dartmouth SYNERGY Clinical and Translational Science Institute is funded by the National Institutes of Health Clinical and Translational Science Award program. This unique facility acts as a research hub for the many colleges and institutes that form the Dartmouth College campus in New Hampshire. A RDM strategy is just one component of the institute; also offered are research bioethics consultations and access to various clinical research supports including a bio-registry. The bio-registry is a virtual depository of the many samples and data sets collected through research conducted at Dartmouth, enabling researchers to access samples from a “freezer-farm” and build on the previous research of others, leading to new clinical and translational science studies.

A key component of the research support offered is the Academic-Industry Core where the Institute works with researchers to foster partnerships with the private sector by supporting the commercial development of research in the biomedical, clinical, health care outcomes and other translational health research fields. The Academic-Industry Core offers intellectual property and entrepreneurial education, other supports for the translation of Dartmouth research into profitable interventions and outreach to private industry including venture capitalist investors.

Economic benefits

The commercialisation of innovative health related research has multiple economic benefits and is only limited by the market demand for the specific intellectual property. Through investment in a strong RDM plan and active relationship building with industry, Dartmouth SYNERGY is able to support researchers and encourage entrepreneurial business development.

Health/social benefits

Research conducted at SYNERGY is intended to be translated into improvements in health care treatments and procedures. Researchers are incentivised to share data and build off the research of colleagues, leading to innovative solutions to complex health care problems that ultimately benefit the public.

Supporting links

<https://synergy.dartmouth.edu/>

Accessed 15 April 2016.